

MECHANISMS OF DIRECTING THE SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: This article contains comments on the technologies of orientation based on the gender approach in preparing and adapting students to social life.

Key words: gender, social activity, sex, socialization, masculinization, phenomenon of alienation, motivation, scientific approach.

INTRODUCTION.

In recent years, large-scale reforms aimed at creating equal rights and opportunities for women and men, ensuring their full participation in the management of society and state affairs, and social, economic and legal support have been implemented in our country. increased. On March 1, 2022, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-81 "On measures to improve the system of working with family and women, neighborhood and religious" and "Family and Decision No. PQ-146 "On organizing the activities of the women's state committee" was signed. Based on these documents, the State Committee for Family and Women and its divisions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, Tashkent city and district (city) are established, and each town, village, village, as well as cities, towns, villages and and in each neighborhood in the villages, the positions of the deputy chairman of the neighborhood for family, women's and social-spiritual issues and the specialist for family and women's issues were abolished, and the position of women's activist was introduced.

In this regard, the 69th goal of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026: provide women with education and professional skills, comprehensive assistance in finding a decent job, support for entrepreneurship, talented tasked with identifying young women and channeling their talents¹.

Modern Uzbek society today is moving towards democratic development. One of the main principles of a democratic society is the recognition of equal rights of women and men in all spheres, which must be formed from a young age. This can be helped by the principles of gender approach in education. In the context of updating the content of education and modernization of general education schools, the problem of gender approach in education and upbringing of a person is becoming urgent.

Gender education helps to solve many important social problems, and the need for its development is increasingly being discussed in pedagogical communities. However, gender mainstreaming is still rare in school education in many countries. In the West, gender education and training begins in kindergarten.

Material and Discussion

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 29, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

Gender segregation exists in modern society, and it is divided into two forms of professional segregation, Horizontal and Vertical segregation, depending on gender. Horizontal segregation occurs when men and women are divided by types of activity. Vertical segregation is the distribution of men and women according to the hierarchy in a certain profession. Gender segregation is carried out depending on the sum of psychological characteristics and characteristics of human social behavior. This often manifests itself in the form of barriers to career advancement for women and men in society². The theory of human capital, the theory of labor market segmentation, and gender theories are used to explain occupational segregation by gender.

According to human capital theory, women's lack of professional experience due to family responsibilities or interruptions in work due to childbirth causes them to be unable to acquire the skills that men possess. It follows that the productivity of women's work is naturally lower. However, with increasing competition, the number of educated and highly skilled workers of both sexes will increase. It is clear that under such conditions, women should be represented in most types of work, otherwise open discrimination against women will occur.

At the same time, the studies of a number of scientists show that parents provide a high level of education for their sons, so women can rarely acquire prestigious professions. The relationship between education and women's professional experience is two-way - despite equal rights in education and career choice, women's opportunities in the labor market are limited.

It should be noted that this theory is gradually losing its relevance, as the average age of marriage in the world has increased and the birth rate has decreased. In addition, most of the household chores are now performed automatically with the help of modern household appliances. These trends help to free up women's career development time and thereby increase their professional experience. However, no significant changes have been observed in the labor market so far, occupational segregation still exists. In addition, employers use hidden discrimination mechanisms. According to women, family obligations prevent direct participation in continuous activities and work. This phenomenon is very common and manifests itself at the recruitment stage. The tendency of employers to discriminate against women formed the basis of G. Becker's theory. According to this theory, the costs of a discriminatory employer are higher than those of a non-discriminatory employer as a result of spending money and time to find only male workers.

Usually, the introduction of a gender approach to the education system is hindered by factors such as ambiguous attitudes in society and the professional environment of teachers, the lack of special knowledge of school teachers in the field of gender pedagogy, and the fact that school curricula and textbooks are created without taking into account gender principles of education. can do. At the same time, scientists say, "In modern society, there is a concept that certain professions belong to men or women"³ and, indeed, the labor market is currently

² Чекалкина А.А. *Гендерная психология*. – Москва: «Ось-89», 2006. – 131 с.

³ Ковалева И.А. *Особенности гендерного аспекта в профессиональной карьере // Психологические науки: теория и практика: материалы Междунар. науч. конф. (г. Москва, февраль 2012 г.)*. URL <https://moluch.ru/conf/psy/archive/33/1916/> (дата обращения: 27.07.2018).

characterized by a high degree of gender asymmetry in the distribution of workers between occupations, which are "female" occupations (stewardesses, teachers, etc.) and "male" occupations (military personnel, programmers, etc.) appears in the presence.

Thus, at present, the gender approach to professional self-determination takes into account not only biological or physical differences between men and women, but also cultural and social aspects. In the research of scientists in the field of gender differences in the professional interests of adolescents, it was noted that the gender characteristics of adolescents affect their career choices.

Sergeeva's research on the gender characteristics of the motivational readiness of teenagers to choose specialized education revealed that there are specific characteristics in the preference of girls and boys. In particular, boys are more interested in "human-technical" professions, and girls are more interested in "human-art" professions⁴.

The analysis of existing studies in the field of gender differences in professional interests of adolescents shows that, despite a sufficient amount of research in the field of professional education of students, the gender aspect of professional interests in young adolescents is an understudied field of scientific research.

Adolescence is one of the main stages of personal development and is accompanied by an identity crisis, within which life, professional and social self-determination takes place. In such conditions, girls and boys develop life views about their position among other people, self-awareness, psychosocial self-determination and readiness to choose a profession. It is during this age period that socio-psychological characteristics, built at three levels, taking into account gender characteristics, are noted:

- internal (accepting oneself as a representative of a certain gender, attitude towards oneself);
- interpersonal relations (perception by peers, attitude towards persons of the opposite sex, etc.);
- interaction with the social environment (relation to relations with persons of the opposite sex, etc.).

The analysis of the results of the study of professional interests among young teenagers showed that the field of professional activity such as "physics-mathematics" is in the first place in terms of the number of choices among boys. and among girls, this field of professional activity received the greatest choice as "chemistry and biology". In our opinion, the existing differences in the fields of professional activity in young adolescents depend on the age and individual characteristics of students, their individual inclinations, their ideas about the variety of professions, and the specific characteristics of teaching and learning. lib, which, in turn, shows the need to carry out targeted work on the formation of professional interests in young adolescents and create favorable conditions for their professional self-determination, taking into account gender differences.

Formation of professional self-determination in the process of studying at school becomes one of the targeted processes of evaluating oneself and one's capabilities in the future professional field. Factors of effective formation of professional self-determination are

⁴ Филиппова С.А. Социально-психологические особенности гендерной идентичности в юношеском возрасте: дис... канд. психол. наук. – Москва, 2009. – 196 с.

specialized forms of education, methods of extracurricular activities, social partnership with vocational guidance subjects, and the educational space in general.

In the field of career and professional orientation in foreign practice, the international creative association "life design" is active, consisting of professional guides from many countries of the European Union. European experts recommend taking into account the "theory of self-construction" and "theory of career construction" in the formation of professional self-determination of young people. A. Watts says that professional support serves both the individual and society as a whole. The process of professional self-determination is the result of many interrelated external and internal factors, including the gender approach⁵.

A survey was conducted among 464 students in the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia) to study the importance of gender in the formation of professional self-determination. The distribution of survey participants by age is as follows: 12-13 years old - 27 people (12.5%), 14-15 years old - 228 people (42%), 16-17 years old - 179 people (31.6%) and 18-19 years old - 30 people (13.9%). Regarding the gender composition of the survey participants, the survey was conducted among 135 boys and 329 girls. Parents and relatives (36%), mass media (34), Internet resources (32), friends and acquaintances (27 %), teachers (22%) and lastly mention books (20%). There are also professional tests (15%), training with employment service specialists (5%).

Mass media and Internet resources, as well as many institutions of society, influence the choice of professions of schoolchildren and reinforce gender stereotypes. For example, in the media, women are mainly portrayed as the object of action, victims, and caring for others, while men are portrayed as inventive, strong, intelligent, and proactive. While the media emphasizes men's strength and success, women are often judged on their appearance. Thus, the mass media, including television, radio, textbooks, children's books, magazines, films, and many forms of electronic communication, perpetuate and propagate stereotypes about men and women.

Also, students E.A. According to Klimov's classification of professions, they answered the questions of the "differential diagnostic questionnaire" methodology, designed for the selection of various professions. The obtained data show the differences between girls and boys in the choice of future professions. Thus, young people mainly choose professions in the fields of "human - technology" (49 percent), "human - signal system" (21 percent) and "human - human" (14 percent). Girls prefer the fields of "person - symbol system" (28 percent), "person - artistic image" (24 percent) and "person - person" (23 percent).

According to career guidance experts, this is due to high school students' classification of professions as "masculine" and "feminine", which significantly affects their professional self-determination. makes a secret. Compared to girls, boys are more clearly oriented towards technical professions. This is consistent with much of the data, which shows that from childhood to old age, men prefer technology-related careers.

According to the results of this questionnaire and methodology, conclusions are made about priority professions among high school students on gender issues. It turned out that the

⁵ Savickas M.L. *Life Designing: A Paradigm for Career Construction in the 21st Century* // *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. 2009. Vol. 75, – № 3. pp. 239-250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2009.04.004>.

boys' favorite subjects are history (43%), computer science (31.2%), chemistry (31%), physics (27%), mathematics (26%), physical education (24%).) and English (21%). Among girls, favorite school subjects are literature (41%), history (33%), social studies (30%) and English (27%). Thus, boys are more interested in the cycle of exact sciences and natural sciences, while girls prefer humanities. Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the most important factors affecting the choice of a profession for students of both sexes are personal characteristics: along with abilities and interests, the advice of parents and relatives, friends and acquaintances is also important.

In conclusion, it was concluded that the vocational training of boys and girls is not a local, but a change of a conceptual nature, because it requires a change in the value system of society, a transition from a sex role to a gender approach in the process of vocational guidance of young people .

If the school continues to prepare boys and girls for various social roles and professions, the situation will not change. Officially, the education system does not prevent boys and girls from choosing a profession. However, stereotypes about the division of occupations into "male" and "female" are instilled into the minds of young people, starting from children's games, through textbooks, home economics classes for girls, and plumber or carpentry for boys. confirms that it continues to play an important role in selection. Therefore, all curricula and textbooks should be presented in a way that does not reinforce gender stereotypes of women.

Conclusions and suggestions:

- ❖ every student and their parents are informed so that they have quality information about future educational and labor market opportunities, to reduce the risk of making decisions based on gender stereotypes, to make the most of the available information will need the help of a consultant;
- ❖ students have different vocational needs at different stages, so access to advice and support needs to be tailored to each student's needs, the school's careers programs are inclusive and diverse should include issues;
- ❖ every student should have multiple opportunities to learn from employers about jobs, employment and skills valued in the workplace. This can be done through a range of enrichment activities including visiting speakers, mentoring and corporate schemes;
- ❖ every student should have first professional experience in the workplace through a business trip, work observation or work experience to explore career opportunities and expand their networks;

all students should fully understand the educational opportunities available to them, including academic and vocational courses, as well as training in schools, colleges, universities and workplaces;

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